

DEVICE SPECIFICATIONS

This section outlines the devices used during the testing, including details of the router and client devices involved in the simulations.

1. Router

Two configurations were set up on the same router model for comparative analysis: one with WPA2 and the other with WPA3 encryption.

Figure 1 router X with WPA2 Configuration

Figure 2 router X with WPA3 Configuration

- Model = NETGEAR EX6120
- Mac Address = A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE
- SSID = 'NETGEAR'
- Encryption = WPA2 & WPA3
- DHCP Server & Subnet = 192.168.100.1/24
- IP = 192.168.100.1

2. Macbook A1502 (Attacker)

The MacBook A1502 is designated as the attacker device, responsible for conducting various attacks such as KRACK and packet injection to evaluate network security.

```
en0: flags=8863<UP,BROADCAST,SMART,RUNNING,SIMPLEX,MULTICAST> mtu 1500
    options=400<CHANNEL_IO>
    ether 8c:85:90:76:e7:34
    inet6 fe80::1ca3:d0c0:f77b:d24d%en0 prefixlen 64 secured scopeid 0x4
    inet 192.168.1.20 netmask 0xffffffff broadcast 192.168.1.255
    nd6 options=201<PERFORMNUD,DAD>
    media: autoselect
    status: active
```

Figure 3 Macbook A1706 as Attacker Device

- Model = MACBOOK A1502
- Mac Address = 8C:85:90:76:E7:34

3. Macbook A1706

MacBook A1706 is one of the client devices connected to the router network and serves as a target for testing the impact of packet injection and sniffing attacks.

```
en0: flags=8863<UP,BROADCAST,SMART,RUNNING,SIMPLEX,MULTICAST> mtu 1500
options=400<CHANNEL_IO>
ether 3c:06:30:2c:d6:21
inet6 fe80::1ca3:d0c0:f77b:d24d%en0 prefixlen 64 secured scopeid 0x4
inet 192.168.100.6 netmask 0xfffff00 broadcast 192.168.100.255
nd6 options=201<PERFORMNUD,DAD>
media: autoselect
status: active
```

Figure 4 Macbook A1706 as Client Y

- Model = MACBOOK A1706
- Mac Address = 3C:06:30:2C:D6:21

4. Windows laptop

The HP Laptop 14s is used as the second client in the network. Like MacBook A1502, it serves as a target for network disruption and monitoring activities during the tests.

```
Wireless LAN adapter Wi-Fi:

Connection-specific DNS Suffix . : lan
Description . . . . . : Realtek RTL8822CE 802.11ac PCIe Adapter
Physical Address. . . . . : 74-12-B3-5E-A5-C1
DHCP Enabled. . . . . : Yes
Autoconfiguration Enabled . . . . : Yes
Link-local IPv6 Address . . . . . : fe80::8104:12ac:5e2f:a710%15(Preferred)
IPv4 Address. . . . . : 192.168.100.4(Preferred)
Subnet Mask . . . . . : 255.255.255.0
Lease Obtained. . . . . : Saturday, 24 August 2024 21:21:16
Lease Expires . . . . . : Sunday, 25 August 2024 09:21:16
Default Gateway . . . . . : 192.168.100.1
DHCP Server . . . . . : 192.168.100.1
DHCPv6 IAID . . . . . : 125047475
DHCPv6 Client DUID. . . . . : 00-01-00-01-28-8F-80-A8-74-12-B3-5E-A5-C1
DNS Servers . . . . . : 192.168.100.1
NetBIOS over Tcpip. . . . . : Enabled
```

Figure 4 Windows Laptop as client Z

- Model = HP LAPTOP 14s
- Mac Address = 74:12:B3:5E:A5:C1

These devices were chosen for their varied operating systems, which allowed for a broader analysis of WPA2 and WPA3 vulnerabilities across different platforms.